

THE IMPACT OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE: CASE STUDY OF SAUDI PORTS AUTHORITY

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ABSTRACT

Every organization's ultimate goal is to improve its performance, and this study has examined the organizational performance of 285 employees from the cargo section of the Saudi Ports Authority in order to achieve that goal. The population of that study consisted of all employees who work in the cargo section of the Saudi Ports Authority. In this study, descriptive statistics were used to gather information. In this research, version 20 of SPSS was utilized as the program for data analysis. The findings indicate that empowerment, better salaries and the practice of recruitment and selection are related in the long run with higher levels of business performance. Organizational performance improvement efforts include compensation management, empowerment, recruiting and selection. The study findings show that the independent and dependent variables are positive relationship..

Keywords: empowerment, compensation management, recruitment and selection, Organizational performance, Saudi Ports Authority

INTRODUCTION

In 1976, the Saudi Ports Authority (Mawani) was founded as a professional work system to construct and manage high-efficiency Saudi ports. Saudi ports have become a major economic provider in only a few years. The Saudi ports have therefore played a key role, with their diverse specialties, in the development and transportation of regional and international trade and passengers, particularly visiting the holy places of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

Ports are vital to a country's economic and strategic interests. They facilitate imports and exports by connecting geographic regions, increasing competitiveness throughout the global supply chain and strengthening the local, regional, and national economies (Song & Parola, 2015). The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA) is the world's biggest and most diverse oil producer with globally orientated industrial exports and the largest and most diversified Middle East economy. In order to complete the task, the KSA should have efficient, fully equipped ports.

It's play an important role in the economic development of import and export freight handling. Elentably (2015) states that 9 major ports in Saudi Arabia represent 95% of all commodity and import exports through Kingdom's seaports and 55% of managed cargoes. In addition, over 5 million TEUs are handled annually, with 11 000 ships visiting Saudi ports (Elentably, 2015). In addition, it is considered as a major player in the global supply and logistics chain as it carries over 90 percent of all cargo transportations worldwide (Mangan & Lalwani , 2016). Despite its positive contribution to Saudi Arabia's domestic growth, cargo over-stock has recently emerged as a major issue, raising cargo handling prices by up to 200 percent and leading to a lack of HRM practices in the cargo section, such as employee recruitment, compensation, and empowerment (Arab News, 2016.).Although, in the port sector, the concept of human resources and organizational performance is gaining popularity (Kattuah, 2013) However, there are few studies on the link between human resource practices and organizational performance, such as those conducted by the Saudi Ports Authority (Alhashedi et al.,2021, Ingrams,2020).

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

This research has assessed the impact of human resources management on the performance of the organizations in the Saudi Ports Authority.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Organizational performance

For small, medium-sized, and large businesses in developed and developing economies to achieve their goals and achieve success, organizational performance is a critical indicator. According to Abdalkrim (2013), the performance of an organization determines how successfully it achieves its goal. Researchers have paid high attention to factors such as financial performance, non-financial performance, or a combination of these two (Crosby,2013). Thus, Companies strive to improve their performance in order to increase the net profit (Singh et al., 2016).

Recruitment and Selection and Organizational Performance

Recruitment and selection is a critical components of a company strategy that identifies and retains the people that are required to thrive and survive in the long run (Ekwoaba et al, 2015).). The primary goal of recruiting is to create a sufficient pool of competent candidates so that the company may select the best candidate by attracting a larger number of workers. However, the key motivation behind the selection process is to select the right way to fill the various organizational positions (Gamage, 2014). Available evidence shows a positive and significant link between the recruitment, selection and execution of a business (Gamage, 2014). For example, Chan (2005) found a positive relationship between selection and business performance. In addition, these positive results were also noted in previous studies (Ichniowski et al., 1995; Katou & Budhwar,2006).

Recruitment, selection and business performance relate positively to each other and performance management programs influence this relationship. The incentive plan and

feedback mechanism are part of the performance management program. The present study suggests that low-level management programs and improper employees lower industrial performance (McDonald & Smith, 1995). The correct recruitment and selection process depends on skills, knowledge, etc. Recruitment and selection are closely related to business performance. Recruitment and selection factors include selection strategies, recruitment, performance evaluation and planning. However Recruitment, selection, and organizational performance, including human resource strategies, all have a direct impact on one another (Koch & McGrath 1996).

Compensation management and organizational performance

Holt (1993) pointed out that employees receive compensation in compensation, pay, and benefits; the output that is used by management is essentially the result of increased organizational performance. The organization's compensation accounts for half of the cash flow, but in the service industry, it accounts for more than half (Ivanceikh & Glueck, 1989). The main component to increase the performance of the organization is to motivate and attract people.

Compensation may take the shape of different compensation schemes and may take the form of individual performance incentives, bonuses and awards. These are the various aspects and components of each compensation and the achievement of multiple payment plans to improve the performance of an organization (Gerhart & Bretz, 1994). According to Lazear (2000), remuneration has a direct impact on employee performance. Employee performance is instantly influenced by compensation and pay structure, which gives pay output in accordance with the pay plan and pay structure.

Gohori et al. (2013) suggested that management supervisory awards have a huge impact on the organization performance, staff performance, improved productivity, employee satisfaction, citizenship behavior and turnover. Money or non-financial payment in the form of prizes or incentives is the most important component for eliminating those who spend their energy in developing innovation for corporate success. Productivity of employees can be increased by motivation, such as compensation, which effectively recognizes improvements in organizational performance (Sandhya & Kumar, 2011).

HRM practices are linked to organizational performance, according to their findings (Ahmad & Schroeder, 2003). Methods of HRM such as selecting recruitment, pay management, training and development, status differentials, decentralization, sharing of information, occupational safety and organizational performance groups such as flexibility, reduced costs, quality and commitment performance. The HR management structure in a US study explores the strong positive association between the organizational performance of various HR activities, such as salary, benefits, recruiting and selection (Gerhart & Trevor 1996).

HRM activities, including as remuneration, empowerment, recruiting and selection and performance management positively affect the performance of the organization (Boselie & Paauwe, 2005).

Hewitt (2009) said that remuneration is the motivating factor for employees; therefore, the proposed compensation structure should pay more employees than average workers with higher performances.

Employee empowerment and Organizational performance

The concept of workplace empowerment has become an important topic in most organisations. It has led to academic debate by human resources and managers who affirm that workplace empowerment enhances organizational performance (Wilkinson, 1998). Efficient employee empowerment techniques and strategies promote positive employee attitudes, contribute to job satisfaction and lead to corporate commitment (Nick et al. 1994).

Employee empowerment offers employees a certain degree of autonomy and decision making for their particular tasks (Dobre, 2013). It enables decision-making at the lower level of an organization in which employees have a unique view on the challenges and problems at the specific level of the organization. Empowerment has become an important theme in management in recent years. The management encourages their employees to be free to use their full potential and their ability to achieve the general goals of the Organization. The value of empowerment has recently been recognized in numerous project management environments (Williams, 1997). Employee performance, on the other hand, is a key element in retaining employees and is closely tied to both the intention to quit and actual turnover.

According to Carriere and Bourque, non-working employees are more likely to leave the company (2009). Though turnover is a multi-stage process, the low organizational performance of many occupational groups in the public sector had a strong and direct impact on intent to quit and actual turnover (Lambert, Hogan, & Griffin, 2007).

Many firms therefore empower their staff to boost the results of corporate performance. Employee empowerment and business performance have a positive relationship, according to Ng'ang and Moronge (2017). In addition, empowerment is a means of reducing decision-making centralization which results in faster processes (Busara, 2016).

Hypothesis

H1: Employee recruitment and selection have a positive relationship with organizational performance.

H2: Compensation management and organizational performance have a positive relationship.

H3: Employee empowerment and organizational performance have a positive relationship.

Conceptual framework

Our study deals with three independent variables, including compensation system, recruitment and selection and employee's empowerment. Whereas organizational performance was the dependent variable. According to Hyde et al. (2008), organization's performance could be affected by different method of human resource practices (Figure 1).

METHODOLOGY

Organizational performance is the focus of our investigation, which seeks to determine the impact of human resources on it. There is main source to offer the information which called secondary and primary source. However, Employees who work in the freight area provide quantitative information as a primary source. Structured questionnaires were used during six months from February to August in 2016 to gather sufficient information. The Authority for Saudi Ports was in charge of conducting the research.

Sample size and Population

The target sector of present study was the cargo section at Saudi Ports Authority. The study's target population includes all employees that work at the cargo section unit of analysis. The 8000 Saudi employees that work in the cargo area considered as a population. According to Johnson and Shoulders (2019), Karanji and Morgan's table (1970) are essential methods in social science studies to determine the sample size based on the population. As a result, the sample size is 367, as shown in the current table. Due to Karanji and Morgan's table, the sample size is based on the population (1970). The convenience sample used non-probability sampling procedures. Because the Saudi port authority lacked a sampling frame, convenience sampling was the most cost-effective option.

Table 3.1
Table for Determining Sample Size of a Known Population

N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S	N	S
10	10	100	80	280	162	800	260	2800	338
15	14	110	86	290	165	850	265	3000	341
20	19	120	92	300	169	900	269	3500	346
25	24	130	97	320	175	950	274	4000	351
30	28	140	103	340	181	1000	278	4500	354
35	32	150	108	360	186	1100	285	5000	357
40	36	160	113	380	191	1200	291	6000	361
45	40	170	118	400	196	1300	297	7000	364
50	44	180	123	420	201	1400	302	8000	367
55	48	190	127	440	205	1500	306	9000	368
60	52	200	132	460	210	1600	310	10000	370
65	56	210	136	480	214	1700	313	15000	375
70	59	220	140	500	217	1800	317	20000	377
75	63	230	144	550	226	1900	320	30000	379
80	66	240	148	600	234	2000	322	40000	380
85	70	250	152	650	242	2200	327	50000	381
90	73	260	155	700	248	2400	331	75000	382
95	76	270	159	750	254	2600	335	1000000	384

Note: N is Population Size; S is Sample Size *Source: Krejcie & Morgan, 1970*

Nature of data, instrument and Analysis technique

The nature of data is quantitative; the Questionnaire method on the 5th Likert scale consists of the following scale given below.

1. Strongly disagree.
2. Disagree
3. Neutral
4. Agree
5. Strongly Agree

There were two sections of the questionnaire: the first part dealt with gathering information about the background of the respondent and second requests for recruitment and selection, compensation management, employees' empowerment and organizational performance. The questionnaire was adopted from previous studies (Masood,2010; Waheed et al.,2013).

Data Analysis

SPSS is a type of data analysis software. It used to compute frequencies and do descriptive analysis, as well as test reliability , validity and correlations. Finally, regression and assess the outcomes of the ANOVA, model summary and coefficient analysis.

Demographic profile

The Saudi Port Authority has 367 employees, notably the cargo section, but data have been collected from 285 employees who have completed the questionnaire correctly. Roscoe (1975) recommends following different thumb guidelines when selecting the sample size. For most studies, one of the principles says that a sample size of greater than 30 but less than 500 is sufficient. There are 180 men and 105 women on the basis of Table 1. The age of respondents, 3%, was under the age of 19. 19.5% between 20 and 29. The age between 30 and 39 years was 34 percent. 28.5 percent were between 40 and 49 years of age, 15 percent were above 50 years of age.24 percent had work experience of less than 5 years.25 percent of franchisees had 5-10 years of experience.70 percent had work experience of 11-5 years.30 per% had work experience of 16-20 years. 8% of employees have over 20 years' work experience (Table 1). The 15% middle, 20% of employees were Senior Managers, 30% younger staff, and 25% other employees.

	Variables	Frequencies	Percentages
Gender	Male	180	83.5
	Female	105	16.5
Age	Below 19	25	3
	20-29	73	19.5
	30-39	80	34
	40-49	57	28.5
	50 above	50	15
Experience	Less than 5 years	20	24
	5-10 years	25	20
	11-15 years	70	12.5
	16-20years	30	17.5
	More than 20 years	50	8
Respondent position	Senior manager	20	3
	Middle manager	15	5
	Junior	30	5
	Staff	25	5

Table 1: Demographic profile.

Descriptive statistics

A range of data including the minimum, maximum and mean describes this central position. In addition, various figures such as range, variance and standard deviation describe this distribution. Finally, the mean value shows the satisfaction of the respondent with franchise management practices for human resources (Table 2).

Statistics		Org. Performance	Empowerment	Recruitment and selection	Comp. Management
N	Valid	285	285	285	285
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		6.6750	8.4650	11.7450	7.0550
Median		6.0000	8.0000	12.0000	7.0000
Std. Deviation		2.76361	3.21097	4.16494	2.65655
Range		12.00	13.00	14.00	12.00
Minimum		4.00	5.00	6.00	4.00
Maximum		16.00	18.00	20.00	16.00
Sum		1335.00	1693.00	2349.00	1411.00

Reliability analysis

The alpha value of the Cronbach scale requires a value of >0.6 ; a value greater than 0.6 is known as a significant value. The reliability of the scale (Brown, 2002).

the Cronbach's Alpha method employed to ensure that the scale is reliable and that its internal consistency is consistent. In other words, when the same test is performed under the identical conditions, the suggested method yielded the same results as our original method (Table 3).

Latent Variable	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha (>0.7)
Compensation Management	9	0.845
Recruitment and selection	9	0.872
Empowerment	8	0.909
Organizational performance	10	0.892

Correlation (Table 4)

Correlations of the Empowerment is closely connected with the value of organizational performance at 0.586. The Commission consequently rejects the null hypothesis that an organization does not have any relationship with its performance.

It also dismisses the null hypothesis of Recruitment and selection, as this is also linked to an organization performing at a value of 350. There is no intermediate relationship but correlation is there.

Correlations of the Compensation management also strongly related to organizational performance of 0.531 and rejects the null hypothesis that it is not connected to the organization's performance. This means that the connection between compensation and an organization's performance can be interpreted as being positive.

There is a large correlation between Pearson and these elements with the performance of an organization, as mentioned above, and the relationship between a Pearson organization and each one above 0.5.

Regression (Table 5)

The Model Summary: As shown here, the regression analysis model includes errors R, R Squared, Adjusted R and Standard Estimates. Pearson R's a subset of R. Pearson R is synonymous with Pearson R². R² is used to evaluate the model's fitness. The measuring factor (sometimes known as the R square) is a statistical element. The R² regressive coefficient is the regression coefficient divided between the square root of the whole square sum, as illustrated in ANOVA Table 5. A R square must be used to compute the amount of variation in the variable. As demonstrated in Table 6, 37 percent of organizational changes are predictive Compensation management, recruitment and selection and employee empowerment. The remaining 62.8 percent may be attributed to unrecognized factors in organizational performance (Antonius,2021).

ANOVA (Table 6)

ANOVA analysis reveals that the model employed to assess the factors affecting organizational performance is statistically significant. Additionally, the above model indicates that the significance threshold is less than 0.05, indicating the existence between the organizational performance and the independent variables.

Coefficients (Table 7)

Unstandardized coefficients (beta and standard error) are included in the coefficient table, as is standardized coefficient (beta), as well as the t value and statistical significance. The beta value, which is the value of the dependent variable, organizational performance, is used to indicate the value of Y. If the independent variables (compensation, employee empowerment, and recruitment and selection) could affect the dependent variable in any way. The t value is statistically significant at a 95% confidence level.

Table 4: Correlation

Correlations					
		ORGP ER	Empowerme nt	Recruitment and selection	and compensation
Pearson correlation	ORGP ER	1.000			
	Empowerment	0.586	1.000		
	Recruitment and selection	0.350	0.456	1.000	
	COMPMANAGE	0.531	0.707	0.558	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	ORGP ER	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
	Empowerment	0.000	.	0.000	0.000
	Recruitment and selection	0.000	0.000	.	0.000
	COMPMANAGE	0.000	0.000	0.000	.
N	ORGP ER	285	285	285	285
	Empowerment	285	285	285	285
	Recruitment and selection	285	285	285	285
	COMPMANAGE	285	285	285	285

Correlation is significant at 0.01 (1-tail).

Correlation is significant at 0.05 (1-tail).

a. **Predictors: (Constant), ORGCITIZEN, EMPDEVELOP, COMPMANAGE,**

b. **Dependent Variable: ORGPER.**

Adjusted R square is based upon the sample size and the number of regressors (constant). The value of the standard error of the estimates is calculated with the help of the Mean square value of the ANOVA Table. The standard error of the estimate is a measure of the accuracy of predictions. The model summary table also includes the Durbin Watson value; it should range from 1 to 4; here value is 2.283 it means there is an autocorrelation between the independent variables. (Vining, G. G. 2001). If its value is exactly two, it means there is no autocorrelation, but here there is some autocorrelation.

Table 5: Regression

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	0.610 ^a	0.372	0.362	2.20710	2.283

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	565.104	3	188.368	38.669	0.000 ^b
Residual	954.771	196	4.871		
Total	1519.875	199			

a. Dependent Variable: Orgper

b. Predictors: (Constant), Compmanage, Orgcitizen, Empdevelop,

Table 6 and 7: ANOVA Coefficients.

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
	(Constant)	1.755	0.530		3.311	0.001
	Empowerment	0.359	0.069	0.417	5.175	0.000
	Recruitment and Selection	0.027	0.046	0.041	0.598	0.550
	Compensation	0.222	0.090	0.213	2.467	0.014

Independent variables, have a significant impact on organizational effectiveness. At 95 percent confidence intervals of empowerment and compensation which is statistically significant with t values of 5.175 and 2.467, respectively, showing a positive connection. However, recruitment and selection is not statistically significant with a t value of 0.598.

FINDINGS

According to the objectives of this study, the compensation management system, recruitment and selection practices, and empowerment all have an impact on the organizational performance of the Saudi Ports Authority, specifically the cargo section. Workers in the cargo sector were asked to fill out a questionnaire as a part of survey. Its objective was to

determine the effect of empowerment, recruitment and selection methods, and remuneration policies on an organization's performance from the employee perspective. The study's findings indicate that implementing more advanced pay management procedures, recruitment and selection practices, and empowerment resulted in improved organizational performance. As a result of their findings, they believe that pay management has a positive effect on organizational effectiveness. Furthermore, the data shows that recruitment and selection processes, as well as employee empowerment, can be used to assess organizational success.

CONCLUSION

The current study presents their outcome based on the analysis due to the research question, objective and hypothesis. In addition, it covered the gap of previous studies. Moreover, the study increased the knowledge of HR practices (Empowerment, Compensation, recruitment and selection), and employees' performance, which is considered as a unique viewpoint in order to lead the organization to achieve a high level of competitive advantage based on proper applied. In addition, the study revealed that employees' performance is an essential part of each organization that could be affected by human resource practices.

In conclusion, the results indicate that human resource practices and employees' performance offered significant contribution to the organization. Thus, the managers should pay high attention to these factors and recognize their employees' once they intend to offer it at the workplace.

FURTHER STUDY

Some areas require additional development in the future, such as topics related to studies that can be conducted on manufacturing companies with a greater number of variables. Numerous aspects should be explored further, including HRM and its impact on change management, the financial performance of the Saudi Arabian public sector, and others.

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